

Agro2Circular

D8.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy

November 2023

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D8.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 8 – Communication & Dissemination activities
Task	T8.1- Communication & Dissemination plan
Lead beneficiary	ICONS
Contributing beneficiary/ies	All partners
Due date of deliverable	31 January 2022
Actual submission date	31 January 2022

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author(s)
0.1	22/12/2021	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini, Nicola Vuolo
0.2	18/01/2022	EURADA,KVC,PRIMA	Jerome Friedrichs Arantzazu Blanco, Barbara Branchini, Irene Garre, M ^a Dolores Fernández
0.3	31/01/2022	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini, Nicola Vuolo
1.0	31/01/2011	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini, Nicola Vuolo First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
2.0	23/11/2023	ICONS	Editorial revision

Summary

The current document is the A2C Communication and Dissemination Plan (Task 8.1: Outreach strategy). It is drafted on the basis of the general description of the communication and dissemination strategy (Annex I of the A2C Grant Agreement, Part B) and the specific Tasks description in the Work Plan Table WP8 of Annex I “Description of Action” of the Grant Agreement (GA).

A sound and comprehensive strategy is described in this document to ensure the good management of the overall communication, engagement and dissemination activities to be performed during the project. This document describes the communication and dissemination strategy developed for A2C project. It outlines the key elements of the communication and dissemination strategy, which include: the targeted audiences (WHO), the key messages to address them (WHAT), the tools and channels employed (HOW), the timing of the planned activities (WHEN) and the geographical level (local, European) (WHERE), hence providing a guide for the project and partners dissemination activities.

At M18, the Dissemination and Communication Plan will be subject to an update (D8.2) to keep pace with the A2C progress, realigning measures and objectives (where needed) and including data and insights from the monitoring activity. The final report on Dissemination and Communication (D8.3) will be released by ICONS on M34.

Introduction

A2C Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Strategy (CDS) will include:

- the stakeholder characterisation and mapping
- the definition of the dissemination phases of the project
- communication and thematic campaigns
- tools, actions, channels, timing and geographical specifications to provide a tailored strategy for each local community and for the wider European context
- KPIs
- Evaluation checkpoints, timing and procedures
- KPIs continuous monitoring and CDS actions effectiveness analysis

C&D activities will be coordinated by the Outreach Manager (ICONS). Local and regional Communication, Dissemination and Engagement activities will be coordinated by the Local Outreach Desk (PRIMA), which will produce a tailored C&D plan to the local context exploiting the most effective tools & channels, and reach local/regional/national stakeholders and communities.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Item	Description
A2C	Agro2Circular
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CEI	Community Engagement Index

1 Communication, Engagement and Dissemination strategy

1.1 Project Objectives and Outcomes

Agro2Circular (A2C) is an EU funded project that will implement a territorial, scalable, systemic and digitally powered solution for the upcycling of fruits and vegetables residues and non-renewable, multilayer plastic into high added value products.

The upcycling of agri-food residues will enhance the use of natural alternatives to synthetic additives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods and cosmetics. This systemic solution and circular economy approach will be tested in the Región de Murcia (Spain) and replicated in two other EU countries (Italy and Lithuania).

A2C solution is **powered by an intensive use of digital technologies** enabling the traceability of all processes, providing a valuable decision tool and fostering citizen's acceptability through data availability and transparency. It **will be constructed upon a systemic approach** delivering a multidimensional model for A2C territorial adoption that is going to be highly replicable and scalable at European level. The adoption and replication of A2C model will be boosted through the delivery of adequate tools at local and European level.

The A2C communication and dissemination (C&D) work runs horizontally across the project lifetime and aims at raising visibility and awareness of the project activities, goals, results, impacts and benefits of A2C across the society.

The following image provides an overview of the D&C activities that will be implemented in order to attain to the expected impacts.

Figure 1- A2C D&C activities and impacts

The main objectives of the communication of A2C are:

- Design the dissemination and communication strategy to support public engagement, project sustainability and the spread of results.
- To spread general knowledge and public awareness about food and plastic waste and the circular economy concept.
- To deliver a framework for autonomous learning and capacity building.
- To implement actions to reach an optimal D&C performance and to periodically assess their implementation and capacity for raising awareness & engagement.
- To support all partners in communicating/disseminating their results and to enhance the transferability potential together with WP7
- Measure the impacts of the developed communication and dissemination activities
- Enable smooth communication and knowledge sharing among the consortium project partners

All the communication activities will boost acceptance and uptake of A2C by transferring knowledge and results emerging from the project towards technical audiences and stakeholders (both at EU and local level) that are likely to be actively involved in the value chain associated with A2C. The general public will be addressed through dedicated

communication and dissemination formats centered on conveying non-technical, easy-to-understand information focused on the benefits brought by A2C.

The following table gives an overview of the difference between communication and dissemination, in terms of objectives, audience, tone of voice and channels.

Table 1- List of dissemination and communication objectives, audiences, tone of voice and channels

	DISSEMINATION	COMMUNICATION
Objectives	Spread the project results and outputs Enhance scientific and social impact of the project and the international projection of the Consortium Ensure sustainability of results	Spread general information on project topics (circular economy, plastic pollution, recycling, food waste) Support dissemination and exploitation Raise engagement of stakeholders
Audience	Academia Policy makers Industry Civil society	Civil society organizations (i.e Fridays for future, consumers associations, environmental organisations) Local communities Individuals
Tone of Voice	Formal	Formal or informal (tailored to audience)
Channels	Website Project deliverables Scientific dissemination (journals, conferences, fairs, workshops)	Website Social media (project and partners') Press Kits Events (workshops)

The collaboration with the Local Outreach Desks (led by PRIMA) will enable the project to reach and engage with local stakeholders, actors and regional authorities through targeted messages and dissemination formats.

ACCOUNTABILITY

Fondazione ICONS, as D&C leader, will create links between relevant A2C contents and specific D&C formats, distributing them through dedicated channels with the aim to maximise its impact in terms of awareness, acceptance and uptake.

1.2 Stakeholder's engagement

A2C success depends on the active engagement of a well-defined community of stakeholders that will be regularly addressed by the consortium partners to facilitate knowledge transfer and share exploitable results.

Dissemination and exploitation strategies will be highly integrated and feed each other to create mutual benefits throughout the different stages of project implementation, aiming to **foster acceptance and uptake of the results produced**. The strategy for stakeholder engagement will follow these steps:

- 1- Identification of key stakeholders:** stakeholders will be first identified among the main actors of the agri-food residues upcycling and plastic multilayer producers and then linked to the most relevant exploitable results, assessing their role and interest them (end-user, customer, enabler, competitor, etc.)
- 2- Analysis and profiling:** for each stakeholder, the reference market will be briefly analysed, in order to understand the priorities in their agenda and collect valuable inputs to convey the respective key messages.
- 3- Design of the strategy:** leveraging on the information collected, targeted dissemination and engagement approaches will be elaborated, defining effective activities to catch their attention, retain it during project duration and make them act as true multipliers for A2C.

All the steps envisaged will be addressed in close collaboration between ICONS as D&C leader, PRIMA as Local Outreach Desk and CETEC as Project Coordinator (PC), with the active support of all the partners.

2 Task 8.1 - A2C Outreach Strategy

2.1 Key communication, Engagement and Dissemination activities (M1- M4, M13-M14, M25-M26)

A2C Communication, Engagement and Dissemination activities are meant to create high impact in terms of: (i) **increase awareness** through easy and accessible information packaged for all target groups; (ii) **enhance acceptance** among end-users, agri-food waste and multilayer plastic experts, stakeholders and policy makers through knowledge transfer tools, networking and clustering activities; (iii) **foster upscaling of results**, paving the way for an effective exploitation of A2C results at European level.

The A2C C&D strategy and activities will follow an integrated, impact-oriented approach. The goal is to raise awareness and boost acceptance and uptake of the A2C key outcomes among the targeted societal groups. To this aim, targeted C&D formats will be designed and implemented to provide a bridge between the project and society.

Figure 2: A2C D&C integrated approach

In order to do so, a multi-level approach (EU and Regional) will be implemented while executing C&D activities. On one hand, the official channels of the project (in English) will be developed and nurtured content wise in collaboration with the consortium as well as to boost the messages further towards their already affiliated audiences, and on the other hand, the Local Outreach Desk will help to foster dissemination at Local and Regional level

(in local language) by co-designing the messages to better reach and engage the local population and key stakeholders.

To reach these objectives in an effective manner, the Communication, Engagement and Dissemination tools and formats will be associated with the right target groups throughout the different stages of project action.

Each target will bring into the project a diverse set of knowledge and expertise. All these categories of stakeholders are expected to extend or replicate the tools and actions provided by A2C once the project comes to an end.

A2C considers the **general public** as a secondary target audience. It poses a different type of challenge, namely the need to adapt technical and highly professional contents into straightforward communication materials. Oversimplification is a risk that will be continuously mitigated and addressed, as it may affect the effectiveness of the messages conveyed and hamper the whole communication process.

The following **key messages**, focused on A2C objectives, have been identified for the project target groups:

Table 2: A2C target groups and key messages

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
Private Organisations and Industry (End-users)	Food	Upcycling Demonstration and scalability	Out of agri-food waste, new food can arise. A2C will develop and test its circular approach in a real case demo site.
	Cosmetic	Upcycling	Agri-food waste can evolve and even become carotenoids for cosmetics.
	Nutraceutical	Upcycling	Out of agri-food waste, new food can arise.

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
	Plastic Producers and recyclers	Upcycling Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated) Demonstration and scalability Traceability Optimisation Digitalisation	A2C will implement biotransformation processes and extensional flow mix for the upcycling of the recycled MPF A2C will provide an economic & environmentally sustainable value chain for the upcycling of F&V residues and multilayer plastic into high added value products A2C will demonstrate a replicable systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy A2C demo site is anchored to the territory, ready to be scaled up
Agrifood Clusters and Associations	Copa-Cogeca	Waste Resource Demonstration and scalability	From the least to the most: a demonstrable and scalable way to find resources in waste.
Industrial associations	European Plastics Converters (EuPC)	Waste Upcycling Demonstration and scalability	A2C will address waste generation by unleashing the value of agri-food residues

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
		Reduction of CO2 emission	<p>New multilayer plastic products: easier to recycle, harder to waste.</p> <p>A2C circular approach will decrease >27,000 Ktonnes CO2 eq emissions</p>
	European Plastics Recyclers (PRE)	<p>Resource Upcycling</p> <p>Demonstration and scalability</p> <p>Reduction of CO2 emission</p>	<p>Why recycle when you can upcycle?</p> <p>New multilayer plastic products as a solid and scalable solution to reduce waste and CO2 emissions.</p>
	Plastics Europe	<p>Upcycling</p> <p>Safety and Stability</p> <p>High quality</p> <p>Demonstration and scalability</p> <p>Reduction of CO2 emission</p>	<p>High quality, high safety, low emissions for A2C solid and scalable production processes of new recyclable plastic products.</p>
Financing intermediaries			<p>A2C will deliver more than 15 new key exploitable results and 30 new circular business models, generating a turnover of 166.8M€</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
Local Markets (short food supply chain)		Value of residues	<p>A2C will deliver tools and methods to value the residues.</p> <p>Keep your path clean for a cleaner future.</p> <p>Your waste is your treasure.</p> <p>Out of food waste, new food can arise.</p> <p>For you is waste, for us a treasure.</p>
Supermarkets		Value of residues	<p>Offering a greener packaging, your good proposal will meet a wider range of clients.</p> <p>Thanks to A2C you will be able to follow the product's lifespan, allowing you to have more supplies' control and transparency toward the final consumer.</p>
Farmers		Traceability Optimisation Digitalisation	<p>A2C will develop an innovative ICT platform functioning as predictive tool for decision support and enabling traceability</p> <p>A2C will help you in performing your daily work at the</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			<p>farm through the ICT platform</p> <p>A2C ICT platform will foster digitalisation in the agri-food sector</p> <p>A2C ICT platform will lead a hand. A2C ICT platform: at your service.</p> <p>A2C ICT platform will make your work more efficient and effective.</p>
Farmers Associations	Confagricoltura	<p>Waste</p> <p>Traceability</p> <p>Optimisation</p> <p>Digitalisation</p> <p>Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)</p>	<p>Farmers can become ambassadors of waste generation reduction through A2C circular approach</p> <p>Thanks to A2C you will be able to follow the products lifespan, allowing you to have more supplies' control and transparency toward the final consumer.</p> <p>A2C circular approach will be shaped around a multidimensional model enabling adoption and scalability of territorial systemic</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			<p>solutions while being sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, fair, boosting urban&regional economies, empowering all actors (citizens, industries, decision makers, academia) and fostering circular practices.</p> <p>A2C will foster digitalisation in the agri-food sector through the development of an ICT platform as decision support system</p>
	Cooperativas agro-alimentarias	Resource Traceability Optimisation Digitalisation Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)	<p>Thanks to A2C you will be able to follow the products lifespan, allowing you to have more supplies' control and transparency toward the final consumer.</p>
	ZLTO	Waste Traceability Optimisation Digitalisation Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)	<p>Thanks to A2C you will be able to follow the products lifespan, allowing you to have more supplies' control and transparency toward the final consumer.</p> <p>A2C circular approach will be</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			<p>shaped around a multidimensional model enabling adoption and scalability of territorial systemic solutions while being sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, fair, boosting urban&regional economies, empowering all actors (citizens, industries, decision makers, academia) and fostering circular practices.</p>
	<p>Coldiretti</p>	<p>Resource Traceability Optimisation Digitalisation Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)</p>	<p>Thanks to A2C you will be able to follow the products lifespan, allowing you to have more supplies' control and transparency toward the final consumer.</p> <p>A2C circular approach will be shaped around a multidimensional model enabling adoption and scalability of territorial systemic solutions while being sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, fair, boosting urban&regional</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			economies, empowering all actors (citizens, industries, decision makers, academia) and fostering circular practices.
Sectorial initiatives and Platforms	CCRI		A2C circular approach tackles the inefficiencies and complexity of sorting and recycling of multilayer plastic films
	EU Cluster Platform		
	EU Circular Economy Vanguard initiative		
	SPIRE	Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)	
	SusChem	Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)	
	European Technology Platform		
Scientific Community	Research/Academic organisations		A2C boosts the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from F&V and MPF) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food and nutraceutical formulation and

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
	Plastic waste valorization science		<p>carotenoids for cosmetic</p> <p>A2C MPF recycling consists of a novel combination of sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination and mechanical recycling.</p> <p>A2C will use biotransformation processes and extensional flow mix for the upcycle of the recycled MPF.</p>
	Researchers		<p>A2C MPF recycling consists of a novel combination of sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination and mechanical recycling.</p> <p>A2C will use biotransformation processes and extensional flow mix for the upcycle of the recycled MPF.</p>
	Trainees		<p>A2C MPF recycling consists of a novel combination of sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			<p>depolymerisation, decontamination and mechanical recycling.</p> <p>A2C will use biotransformation processes and extensional flow mix for the upcycle of the recycled MPF.</p>
Decision Makers	Public administrations	<p>Safety</p> <p>Circular economy</p> <p>Policy and Regulation</p> <p>Traceability</p> <p>Optimisation</p> <p>Digitalisation</p> <p>Job creation</p> <p>Reduction of CO2 emission</p>	<p>A2C boosts the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from F&V and MPF) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food and nutraceutical formulation and carotenoids for cosmetic</p>
Financing bodies			<p>Investing in a sustainable economic model for the future of agriculture. A2C solid, safe and scalable solutions for agri-food waste upcycling and multilayer plastic product recycling will provide an</p>

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			economic and ecological greener future.
Standardisation bodies			Let's sustainability be the norm in EU regulation of food waste upcycling and multilayer plastic recycling.
EU/Regional/National development agencies	European Plastics Recycling and Recovery Organisations		Circular business models are key for Sustainability
Local/Regional/EU initiatives	Lifegate	Territorial Demonstration Upscale	A2C proposes innovations in the fields of Circular economy, ICT and sustainable entrepreneurship, through a systemic solution
Citizens	Teachers For Future Mothers for Future	#Zerowaste Safety Circular approach (VS landfill & incinerated)	Current recycling technologies are still inefficient and need to be improved A2C: new solutions for a better planet A2C solutions productions will create new jobs. [will the jobs and the factories have a greener impact on workers and the country where they'll be based?] Help us tracing a new roadmap for

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
			<p>the next generations.</p> <p>Help us to make a clearer path for our children.</p> <p>What goes around, turn around. Do not allow the past's bad practices to haunt your future.</p> <p>[green and handy] As you want it.</p> <p>Do not change your habits, change the planet.</p>
Students		PassOnPlastic, Recycle	<p>Lots of waste can be avoided in our daily life</p> <p>We can choose food and beverages packaged in recyclable materials</p> <p>Packaging still has a long life to live: choose food and beverage wrapped in recyclable materials.</p> <p>Don't trash your life, don't trash our planet: avoid unnecessary waste.</p>
Civic Society Organisations	Plastic Free ANSE (Asociación Naturalistas del		[will the jobs and the factories have a greener impact on workers and the

Type	Detail	Keyword	Key Message
	Sureste), Ecologistas en Acción, Procabo, Asociación Ambiente Europeo Asociación Murcia Limpia		country where they'll be based?] Go separate ways: decoupling economic and human activities from the consumption of finite resources.

2.2 Dissemination and Communication tools and channels

A2C implements an integrated and **impact-driven communication and dissemination approach** with a multi-actors and multi-channel strategy. The communication tools were chosen to be the most effective to reach the project's target audience.

2.2.1 Visual identity and brand book

A2C logo and visual identity are based on the result of a brand personality exercise in which the coordinators of the project were actively involved. The aim of the brand personality exercise was to highlight the features, characteristics and elements that make A2C stand out as a European research and innovation project.

The project logo, a set of icons, graphic elements, images, infographics, social media GIFs and cards, templates for presentations and reporting will be designed to reflect the project's values, key messages and characteristics.

Different options for the logo and the visual identity (available in Annex 1) were developed by ICONS, based on the results of the brand personality exercise. These options were presented to the project's coordinator to choose the final version of A2C logo:

Figure 3- Agro2Circular logo

The official project brand book is the document listing all the guidelines on how to use the project logo and the visual identity material. It is a rulebook for everyone involved in the creation of communication and dissemination material for A2C. Partners are encouraged to follow the brand book guidelines when communicating A2C or presenting the project at events, training courses and workshops for stakeholders. The brand book will be published and released among the partners and will be available on the project website. Below, an example of visual identity guidelines from A2C brand book:

<p>ACCOUNTABILITY</p>	<p><i>A2C logo and brand system have been developed by ICONS with feedback from CETEC (Task 8.2- Visual identity).</i></p> <p><i>All project partners are encouraged to use the logo and the rest of the brand materials under the supervision of ICONS, following the graphic guidelines provided in the brand book.</i></p>
<p>ASSOCIATED DELIVERABLES</p>	

All dissemination items and publications released by A2C, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the Research Executive Agency (REA) under Grant Agreement N° 101036838. All A2C publications will include the following statement (from GA section 29.4): *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838”* and display the EU emblem.

All infrastructures and project’s major results will include the statement: *“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the*

European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838".

2.2.2 Website and Landing page

A temporary **landing page** was designed and released by ICONS on the **30th of November 2021 (M2)**. The landing page provides all the essential information about the project and its main contacts. The following image represents the landing page developed.

Figure 4: A2C Landing page

A2C website will be launched in **January 2022 (M4)**, displaying the project logo and visual identity. The website is A2C main online communication channel, being the first interface tool for the project's different target audiences. A2C main contacts, the newsletter subscribe button and the links to the social media channels will be provided in the website footer. The website will have the same URL as the temporary landing page: <https://agro2circular.eu>.

The website is a **flexible tool** that will be **constantly updated** to meet A2C needs throughout the entire duration of the project. To guarantee this flexibility, A2C website is designed in WordPress. It will include the **project's original contents** and links to relevant

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material produced by **external sources**. Specific material will be produced and published on A2C website to raise **general public** interest and awareness on the project and its future outcomes. **Professionals** will be addressed through dedicated dissemination products. The website aims to increase stakeholders' awareness, acceptance, uptake on A2C project and to attract the attention of potential stakeholders. **All the website contents will be accessible to the viewers with no restrictions.**

A2C website will have a specific session dedicated to the **A2C cluster** with contents developed in Spanish and **managed by the Local Outreach desk**. The website will establish a link to the stakeholder platform as a two-way communication tool. The management of the website contents will be backed up by a social media strategy (e.g. LinkedIn and Twitter).

A2C domain “agro2circular.eu” was registered in October 2021.

Registered users' contact details will be treated as fully confidential, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). ICONS will act as the Data Controller to ensure that the sensitive information of the stakeholders and users registered in the online platform/website will remain strictly confidential. Followers' contact details are used uniquely for the dissemination of A2C project and for no other purpose. Users are granted the right to access the information they provided upon online registration and to decide to opt out from the project contact list at any time.

Table 3: List of website sections

Website sections:	Objective
Homepage	Provide with a comprehensive and catchy entry-point to A2C contents
News and Events	Promote news and events from and related to the project
Resources	Include downloadable outcomes from the project (such as, public deliverables, reports, C&D materials...)

ACCOUNTABILITY	<p><i>Both A2C landing page and website are developed and looked after by ICONS, with input and feedback from CETEC. Input and co-operation from CETEC and the rest of the A2C partnership are encouraged to feed regular updates into the website.</i></p> <p><i>In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the Data Controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by the registered users upon online registration.</i></p>
ASSOCIATED DELIVERABLES	

2.2.3 Media multipliers

External platforms will be used as multipliers to disseminate A2C contents that are of general interest. These platforms have syndication agreements with ICONS. The commonly used multipliers are AlphaGalileo and Phys.org. Additional channels will be included if their focus is on the topic covered by A2C.

Journalistic articles, interviews and press releases are among the outreach products to be distributed through media multipliers (Task 8.4).

For each of the communication materials produced by the project, ICONS will monitor and quantify their outreach to understand the interaction and level of engagement triggered by news, press releases and journalistic articles. ICONS will collect outreach and engagement data from all the media multipliers that have a data sharing policy.

A2C consortium partners are encouraged to republish the project's press and news releases via their own networks. For monitoring purposes, they will have to inform ICONS once they re-distribute these products.

ACCOUNTABILITY	<p><i>ICONS will be responsible for distributing and monitoring the news and press releases and journalistic articles to external news multipliers.</i></p>
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The consortium partners are encouraged to re-distribute these materials within their networks.

2.2.4 Social networks

A comprehensive social media strategy will support the project website, assessing the most efficient channel to reach the target audiences. Social networks are fundamental channels to communicate the project, its goals, activities and results, and to engage with different communities. Among others, a dialogue will be established with the project partners, the social media accounts managed by Agro2Circular's partners, the leading stakeholders and influencers belonging to the Agro2Circular's pillars, the EU Commission, all the networks and associations with whom cooperation and open communication channels have been established. For each target specific channels, tone of voice and contents will be defined.

A2C social media account for **Twitter** was created by the 25th of October 2021, for the Kick-off meeting, and it will be updated throughout the whole duration of the project. Consortium partners' existing social media channels will be widely exploited to foster outreach and engagement towards their existing stakeholders' communities and local actors around A2C. To catch and retain public's attention, A2C Twitter channel ([@Agro2Circular](#)) will produce **regular tweets** on the project's main results: public deliverables, scientific publications, details and follow-up news about training organised by the project, progress made by the project, and facts worth bringing up.

Figure 5: A2C Twitter

The **official hashtag** #agro2circular has been set to track the impact of the social media conversations about the project. The hashtag was presented during the kick-off meeting in October 2021 and all partners are invited to use it. This hashtag will be used to monitor posts about A2C, to gather quantitative and qualitative impact data.

ACCOUNTABILITY	<p><i>ICONS will be responsible for the core social media activities: setting up the accounts, posting, following existing social media channels and monitoring outreach. Specific social media campaigns (also, addressing local stakeholders and citizens) will be coordinated and organised with PRIMA.</i></p> <p><i>The consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by joining the community of A2C social media followers. They can retweet and repost our content from their organisations' channels and use the #agro2circular.</i></p>
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3 Task 8.3 - Communication and Engagement at local and regional level (M5- M36)

The Local Outreach Desk will be coordinated by PRIMA and, with the support of ICONS, will be in charge of local communication and engagement actions and campaigns in line with the public and citizen engagement strategy (Task 7.1).

Citizen engagement is here understood as a process of institutional and citizens' transformation, in which the participation of the quadruple helix of open innovation (encompassing administration, business, research and education and citizenship) plays a key role. Suitable resources and key actors from the quadruple helix will be selected to benefit from synergies and to avoid an overlapping of measures or the overburden of the selected actors.

The process of citizen engagement entails different levels of public participation based on the Spectrum of Public Participation developed by the International Association of Public Participation (IAP2)¹ as reflected in the figure below. The levels of participation range from the left of the Spectrum, with low participation (where stakeholders are simply informed about problems and solutions, i.e through websites or social media) to the right of the spectrum with high participation degree (in which stakeholders are empowered to take decisions, i.e referendums)² These levels are discrete degrees and each of them will be appropriate depending on the context, the project stage and the target users.

The actions planned in A2C will be analysed together during WP7 Meetings to select the level of participation according to the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity. To this end, partners involved (KVC, PRIMA) will collect data from the partnership during meetings that will be used in the first step (analysis).

- **Inform:** These actions are aimed at providing the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions. Inform level is considered as transversal across the spectrum of

¹ <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>

² Ostling, Alina & Francoli, Mary & Steibel, Fabro. (2016). From Informing to Empowering: Improving Government-Civil Society Interactions within Open Government Partnership (OGP).

processes, since effective engagement requires a strategic flow of information.

Examples: lectures and seminars in educational institutions

- **Consult:** These actions are aimed at obtaining public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions, but with little interaction. This level is appropriate when specific input is required by the public but early engagement is not possible. The targeted public is informed about how their feedback influenced the decision. Examples: interviews, surveys and questionnaires on packaged food consumption and recycling behaviours.
- **Involve:** Actions at this level require working with the public to ensure that concerns and needs are understood and considered, by means of a two-way exchange of information and discussion and providing opportunities to influence the outcome. Decisions at this level are made by the administrations, although the issues raised should be taken into account. Examples: focus groups, study circles.
- **Collaborate:** actions in which the public is directly engaged in decision making and involved in the interactive process, often including an attempt to find consensus solutions. These actions require creating trust and ensuring a genuine engagement, being costly and time-consuming while implying risks that can damage future relationships with key stakeholders. Examples: Co-creation forums, Delphi studies, circular economy governance desks, generation of a video documentary.
- **Empower:** At this level, the public is given the opportunity to make decisions for themselves. At this level, a decision could be made by the community through a process that requires little interaction, such as a referendum or voting measure. The level promises to implement what you decide. In the agro2circular framework, this level corresponds to the stakeholder panel, including representatives of organizations, industrial companies, and associations which are relevant in the A2C's results uptake, such as environmental or consumer associations.

Figure 6:Public participation toolkit. Source: IAP2

Specific actions have already been proposed by local partners:

Table 4: A2C local partners communication and engagement actions

A2C partners:	Communication and engagement actions:
PROEX	Engagement plan to raise local and regional primary agricultural stakeholders' awareness through targeted actions
AGRO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conferences and workshops targeting both the local and regional industrial sector, facilitating their circular economy approach - Administrative support desk to support the local and regional industrial sector <p>Tailored events to engage the general public</p>

PRIMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lectures/workshops at regional schools, universities and educative events to raise awareness on A2C topics (M9-M20, twice/weekly) - Pending to assess the availability and need and frequency of this activity. - Regional contests for scholars aimed to spread the circular economy approach and fostering their involvement in these practices - Short documentary production involving several actors (Alhama de Murcia municipality, local companies, students), arising awareness about project topics and fostering community engagement on circular and climate neutral practices <p>A youngster video game production, based on the waste management of products linked to the circular economy</p>
A2C partners:	<p>Communication and engagement actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Surveys and questionnaires regarding package consumption habits and recycling behaviours - Focus groups with different stakeholders (administration, civil society, industry) exploring barriers and opportunities at the local and regional level

Additionally, communication will focus on local and regional dissemination of results through content packaging and relations with key stakeholders, stimulating social acceptance and replication. Dedicated publications will be produced for local and regional dissemination, as well as edited, easy to read Public Deliverables. PRIMA, together with the rest of the collaborators in this task, will disseminate the materials produced by ICONS.

ACCOUNTABILITY

KVC, PRIMA will be in charge of the design and execution of communication and engagement activities.

4 Task 8.4 - Outreach and European level (M1-M36)

To disseminate A2C results, the following materials will be developed by ICONS, including:

- A biannual **e- Newsletter**;
- A dedicated, easy-to-read, **info-packs** supported by visual tools (e.g. infographics, factsheets) with dedicated content for each target group;
- Abstracts of **key Public Deliverables**, conveniently edited to facilitate their dissemination;
- The project's final publication: **A2C Best Practices Book**, in both electronic & printable format. It will include guidelines, lessons learnt and recommendations;
- **Scientific & technical** publications.

Public outreach contents will be developed to address the general public, including citizens and other general stakeholders. These contents aim for widespread distribution through European and global media and information multipliers and will be packaged through the following communication formats:

- **Press and news releases**, to increase A2C visibility and to promote events related to and organised by the project;
- **Independent journalistic articles** (2) on A2C and project related topics;
- Audio- video productions: a series of **short video- interviews** with project experts, stakeholder's representatives and decision- makers;
- A **final video** for web distribution, featuring A2C outcomes;
- **Dedicated social media campaign** at EU and global level for thematic World Days and other EU initiatives.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will be in charge of the production and execution of tailored D&C formats and all A2C partners will support by providing inputs and suggestions (related to contents).

5 Task 8.5 - Networking and clustering activities (M5- M36)

A2C participation in networking events and engagement in clustering activities at regional and European level will increase the project's visibility among the relevant stakeholders and segmented target groups.

A final event will take place at the end of the project to share A2C main results and lessons learnt with stakeholders and similar projects.

Specifically, A2C consortium will seek to mobilise and integrate key European stakeholders (industry, academia, consumer associations, NGOs) to promote the project's linkage with European fields of action and initiatives at different levels, such as Circular Economy Action Plans and the European Bioeconomy and Industrial Strategies. Networking and clustering activities will be led by EURADA.

To this end, A2C will initiate B2B meetings, organise events at EU level, such as workshops and other dissemination events, as well as participate in external events – again at multiple levels. Special emphasis will be put on clustering activities with other relevant European projects and initiatives in the field of circular economy, for example the A2C sister projects funded under the same call/topic. The aim of these clustering activities will be to identify synergies and to promote dialogue and exchange of good practices between the involved project actors and stakeholders. Furthermore, close collaboration with the CCRI will be sought to maximise the impacts of networking and clustering activities and to guarantee the dissemination of project results on a wider scale and among a wider audience.

6 Dissemination and Communication formats

6.1 Flyer and printouts

The project flyer will be produced at M8 by ICONS as supporting material to inform stakeholders on A2C objectives and expected impacts, involved partners and contact details.

Its visual identity will be consistent with the project visual identity developed at M2. Project partners will be in charge of translation of the flyer in their own local language to foster local distribution during dedicated local fairs, workshops, conferences, events and roadshows. A .PDF version of the flyer will be available for download in the resource section of the project website.

Additional communication materials such as roll- ups, posters, banners etc will be developed on demand according to the partners' needs. All these materials will be printed for distribution during the events. However, due to the possible limitations posed by the COVID-19 pandemic to physical events across EU countries and regions, the number of printed materials will be carefully assessed in due course.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will be in charge of the development and the design of the flyer. This will be done in cooperation with CETEC, who will provide the text of the flyer.

ICONS will be in charge also for the design and development of all the supporting communication materials (posters, roll- ups, banners etc).

All the other partners will provide any further information that may be necessary for the development of the flyer. They will be asked to translate the texts of the communication materials in their local language if needed.

6.2 Training material

Communication material will be produced for local events and training activities organised by local partners. These materials will be distributed before and after the event to raise awareness and foster outreach of the activities carried out, lessons learnt, interesting stories and innovation implemented in the demos.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will support the project coordinator and local partners in organising the training activities. The latter will actively cascade information about the training down to business and research stakeholders in their community.

The content of the training and support materials will be produced by CETEC, UVEG (Task 8.6 leader) and the technical partners involved in this task. ICONS will take care of the layout.

6.3 Newsletter

A2C newsletter (Task 8.4) will be issued every 6-month basis, starting on M6. People can subscribe to it via the website, in compliance with the GDPR guidelines.

The newsletter is a tool designed to reach both the professional community and the general public. It will be in English, in HTML format. The newsletter will contain project updates and main achievements in the form of articles, news and press releases. Upcoming activities, workshops and events will be advertised. All partners will be asked to send to ICONS relevant news and events to be included in the newsletter.

All newsletter's issues will be available on the website, promoted via social media and the partners' networks.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will be in charge of developing the contents to be featured in the project newsletters in cooperation with the rest of A2C partners. ICONS will also take care of sending it to the online registered users.

6.4 Videos

A series of short video interviews with project experts, stakeholders' representatives and decision-makers will be produced by ICONS (Task 8.4 – Outreach at European level). The videos will be in English and they will be accessible via website and distributed via social media, communication portals, platforms and events.

Moreover, towards the end of the project, **ICONS will produce a final video, in English, on A2C main outcomes.**

ACCOUNTABILITY

*ICONS will produce all the videos, developing and distributing them.
Input from CETEC and the technical partners will be asked to integrate the content.*

6.5 Journalistic articles and interviews

Professional journalists (2) will cover topics linked to A2C, writing independent journalistic articles and interviews. These tools aim to reach a broad audience.

The independent journalistic articles and interviews will be published on A2C website. Moreover, they will be distributed to the public at a European and at a global level using different multipliers or platforms, namely youris.com, phys.org, Worldnews and AlphaGalileo. Their outreach and engagement will also be fostered through A2C and partners' social media channels.

The articles and the videos are meant to reach both the general public and the professional community, raising the public's awareness and acceptance of the project.

ACCOUNTABILITY

The editorial production will be discussed by ICONS with CETEC. Contents will originate either from external sources collected by journalists (during their investigation) or directly from A2C project. ICONS will take care of the distribution.

6.6 Press and news releases

The press and news releases **will focus on specific project issues and milestones, promoting project events and progress, drawing stakeholder's and public's attention towards A2C project.** All the press and news releases will be available to local partners for translation into local languages and distribution through their existing channels.

News releases will be used to inform the audience of the participation of some members of A2C consortium to external events and to present their latest project findings and achievements. Both the press releases and the news releases will be published on the project website and, whenever the content is particularly relevant, they will be distributed to external online resources and news multipliers (like AlphaGalileo).

ICONS will be collecting and monitoring on a six-months basis all publications released by partners through a dedicated template.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will be responsible for producing and distributing press releases and news releases.

All A2C partners will flag up to ICONS interesting aspects worth covering by press or news releases, by providing them with the necessary details and background information. ICONS will draft them and take care of their distribution.

Once they are ready, the other members of the consortium will be encouraged to further distribute them through their own portals, newsletters or other appropriate channels.

6.7 Scientific publications

A2C is expected to generate scientific results to be disseminated in Scientific Conferences and Technical Journals. A2C papers will feature all findings from the academic and technological partners of A2C within the project. Scientific papers should be published in open access (clause 29.2 of the Grant Agreement).

News about the release of A2C scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the project website and its social media channels.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will keep track of all the scientific and technical publications made by A2C scientific and technical partners within the project. ICONS will promote them via the Project Website and social media.

Research, industrial and technical partners will be the main responsible for the release and publishing of Scientific Papers.

6.8 Infographics, Factsheets and Best Practice Book

Infographics and factsheets will be produced for the technological solutions and circular approach implemented in A2C pilot. They are meant to be easy to read and with an appealing graphic, targeting end-users, circular economy experts, stakeholders and policy makers. They will be distributed via the project's online communication channels, external multipliers and 1-to-1 communications through the registered users to the project website.

At the end of the project, a **Best Practice Book** will be produced, in both electronic and printable format. This document will contain the project's major achievements and recommendations and it will highlight the benefits for each identified target.

ACCOUNTABILITY

ICONS will be in charge of the production of infographics, factsheets and the best practice book.

Research, industrial and technical partners will be the main responsible for the scientific texts of these products. ICONS will facilitate data collection.

ICONS will promote the release of infographics, factsheets and the best practice book via the Project Website and social media.

7 Management of communication and KPIs

To ensure that EU-wide communication activities can reach out to the identified stakeholders and the general public, **full cooperation needs to be established between the C&D Leader (ICONS) and the rest of the consortium.** Strong interaction is expected between the project dissemination and communication, illustrated in the current document, and the partners' local activities, especially addressing stakeholders and professional audiences: therefore, full cooperation from the rest of the team is required.

ICONS will lead the **Dissemination and Communication Secretariat (DCS)**, namely the central office coordinating all contacts towards stakeholder communities and other exploitation, dissemination and communication target audiences, including social media. The DCS will liaise with all the local contact points to define D&C strategies at local level, leveraging both on existing D&C channels and tools (facilitated by local partners) and on communication assets specifically set up to guarantee coverage, distribution and impact of A2C contents.

The role and responsibility of ICONS, the project coordinator and all the other members of the A2C consortium have been indicated in the current document in the "Accountability" text boxes at the end of each chapter.

All the A2C partners should be committed to the C&D activities. They will be encouraged to promote relevant information, outcomes and milestones towards their audiences by using their own dissemination and communication channels (such as, websites, social media, newsletters, etc.).

Through the Local Outreach Desk and other established links with the communication officers of the partners' organisations, the information will be shared for broader outreach, possible uptake and promotion beyond the official channels directly managed by the project. Project's actions, activities and results and information will be distributed according to the target addressed. The Local Outreach Desk will help to distribute more tailored communication messages to specific local stakeholders and citizens, while the project partners will promote the results and achievements within their websites to reach out to their own audiences.

7.1 Local Outreach Desk

A Local Outreach Desk will be key to spur outreach and engagement opportunities within the local audiences. They will help to distribute more tailored communication messages to specific stakeholders and the population, while the project partners will promote the results and achievements within their websites to reach out to their own audiences.

The local outreach desk (Task 8.3) aims to foster local dissemination, engagement, and co-creation activities (in synergy with Task 7.1), to boost project outreach and sustainability at local level. PRIMA will coordinate the local outreach desks activities and will be the main link between the WP8 leader and local partners.

The task of the Local Outreach Desk includes:

- Co-design the Communication & Dissemination Strategy at a local level (in synergy with WP8 leader)
- Disseminate the core project messages through local networks and channels
- Adapt these messages to the local ecosystem
- Inform WP8 leader of local initiatives, events related with A2C and progress of the project activities
- Produce relevant content at a local level that might be disseminated at a central/European level
- Monitoring and reporting the local communication and dissemination activities

7.2 C&D KPIs

The following table gives an overview of the KPIs that will be met by A2C consortium through dissemination and communication activities.

Table 5: A2C D&C&E KPIs

Activity	KPI
Networking and clustering actions (local, regional, EU & international level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in external events (technical/scientific/transversal fairs, congresses, conferences, joint webinars, roundtables, workshops) >60; • Mobilization of key European and international stakeholders & associations (+100);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B2B meetings (>200), clustering with other circular territorial clusters and EU projects/initiatives (>50). • Alliances with civil society organizations (>30 CSOs); • A2C Organized events>20: A2C final event, tailored workshops for targeted stakeholders, joint webinars, A2C technology demonstrative events.
Knowledge transfer/training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 mentoring programme for regional industries; Individual assessments to regional industries; • Organized actions aimed to knowledge transfer (practical guidelines for clusters/industries, guidelines fostering public engagement, CE and decision makers recommendations and environmental education)>20
Actions specially fostering public engagement at all levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement campaigns, Cross-fertilization activities • co-creation workshops/focus groups (WP7), 1 • community based innovation scheme (WP7), 1 • local/regional engagement plan agri-food sector, 1 • circular economy support desk for regional industries, 1. • Tailored lectures/workshops (>20), • youngster's regional contests (>8), • short documentary (>1, translated), • video games (>1, translated).

8 Monitoring of Engagement

The measurement of the impact of communication and engagement actions is based on the number of people that make use or come across a specific communication product and the number of their interactions. Outreach and engagement quantitative indicators therefore constitute the principal instrument to assess the impact of the A2C project on its target audience.

- **Outreach indicators** measure online and offline communication reach with the aim of strengthening the impact on awareness. They are basic indicators that on their own do not provide a complete picture of A2C effectiveness, but rather a starting point for deeper analyses.
- **Engagement indicators** measure activities associated with A2C communication. They help in understanding the impact of A2C communication messages on target audiences with the aim of boosting acceptance. They provide a powerful tool to assess the effectiveness of A2C communication.

Considering these broad definitions, A2C takes a comprehensive multi-dimension monitoring approach to outreach and engagement indicators, defining their impacts at different levels:

- Publications, including articles, interviews, videos, page flows, news and press releases
- Project website (<https://agro2circular.eu>).
- Social media leveraged in the project (Twitter, LinkedIn)
- Webinars organised during project execution
- Workshop and events, carried out during project execution
- Other, to cover other impacts which cannot be categorised above

The integration between outreach and engagement data across these 6 above-mentioned impact areas constitutes the basis for an integrated analysis of the overall impact generated by the project activities, which will be analysed in the Periodic Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities.

Tools that will be used to monitor outreach and engagement will be Google analytics, Twitter analytics, LinkedIn analytics and Nuvi®, a dedicated social monitoring tool.

Google Analytics will allow you to monitor the website performance in terms of visitors, page views, number of sessions, access points etc. The information collected is one element of

the overall monitoring and impact assessment campaign which will be carried out by ICONS over the course of the whole project.

8.1.1 Outreach measurement

Outreach data provide a quantitative assessment of the impacts in terms of awareness. Outreach data are monitored on web, social and during workshops and events. Web monitoring is performed by the project according to different approaches:

- Direct monitoring, by retrieving data on the web traffic (and views) for the A2C public communication products (articles, interviews, press and news releases, videos) from the A2C website and platforms working in syndication with WP8.
- Direct monitoring of social media accounts managed by the project through social media analytics tools and the use of dedicated state-of-the-art software tools, such as Nuvi®.
- Indirect monitoring, by identifying the referrals made on A2C materials by other on-line and social web resources. A more sophisticated analysis of top influencers mentioning and retrieving A2C posts will be made possible by the use of Nuvi®.

Outreach will also include the number of people reached through off-line dissemination and communication activities (such as number of participants at conferences/fairs where A2C is represented, number of citizens participating at local events, etc.).

The outreach data retrieval will be aimed at the definition of the impact data, which will provide an input to the definition of the Community Engagement Index.

8.1.2 Community engagement monitoring and measurement

Engagement indicators, measuring activities of the users associated with A2C's communication products are:

- For publications: Number of likes, shares, comments, clicks related to each publication on website, social media, other platforms. Number of downloads if allowed by the platforms leveraged.
- For social posts: Number of likes, shares, comments, clicks related to each post.
- For website: Number of page views lasting more than 1 minute.

- For webinars and events: Number of participants to local events. Number of follow up requests.

To measure the effectiveness of engagement, ICONS has developed the Community Engagement Index (CEI). This index integrates all communication activities (i.e. publications, project website, social media, webinars, workshops/events, and other activities) into a single metric. It represents the level of interest and engagement generated by A2C considering the overall community the project is able to generate through its different activities and describes their overall impact. The CEI therefore takes into account total outreach and related activities animating the community, representing the total engagement of the A2C community in the topics covered by the project.

It is worth stressing that CEI measures the engagement of a community with a content. It doesn't describe the overall effectiveness of A2C communication activities, but only their engagement rate. Low values of the CEI indicate little interest by the target audience (compared to its outreach), while high values suggest high interest and engagement of the community in that specific content.

To improve the effectiveness of the communication activities, ICONS leverages its Communication Effectiveness Quadrants, which plot publications (but also social posts, web pages, events, etc) in 4 quadrants depending on their total outreach and engagement and consider the related PEI to identify most successful communication outputs and potential pitfalls and take corrective actions whenever needed.

9 Conclusions

This Communication & Dissemination Plan is a flexible living plan. The communication strategy aims at maximizing the dissemination materials and activities, ensuring that key stakeholders receive the information and benefits of the project. It also allows the project team to adapt to future developments, especially the lessons learned from the first period of the project.

The C&D activities are of crucial importance for the project itself and its sustainability. Mapping, reviewing, monitoring, and validating them in a living plan is essential.

The present version will be subject to one update over the course of the project (D8.2 - M18) and the final version will be released towards the end of the project (D8.3 – M34). This will allow the overall communication and dissemination strategy to be adjusted according to the evolution and needs of the project.

Annex 1. A2C visual identity concepts

Option A | Visual concepts: Creation – Protection – Unveil

Option B | Visual concepts: Fruit and vegetable – Packaging – Circularity

Option C | Visual concepts: Circularity – Organic – Protection

Annex 2. Events' template

A2C EVENTS												
Partner Short Name	Partner's role	Type of event	Title of the event	Date	Place					Countries addressed	URL	How was Agro2Circular presented?
						Scientific Community	Industry	Policy makers	Total audience			
WETSUS	Attendee	EXHIBITION	Aquatech Amsterdam, world's leading water trade show for process, drinking and wastewater	02/11/21	Amsterdam, Netherlands				15000	International	https://www.aquatechtrade.com/amsterdam/	Poster
CTNC	Speaker	OTHER	II Day of meetings with iWATERMAP project partners	04/11/21	Murcia, Spain	x	x	x	15	EU		Presentation
CETBIO	Speaker	TRADE FAIR	INNOVAM+	09/11/21	Cartagena, Spain	x	x	x	300	National	INNOVAM+Website	Presentation
INFO	Other	OTHER										

Annex 3. Digital Communication

Partner Short Name	Website	Twitter Channel involved in dissemination of projects' contents (link)
KVeloce	https://kveloce.com	https://twitter.com/Kveloce_ID_i
EURADA	https://www.eurada.org/	https://twitter.com/Eurada_RDAs
EVERSIA	Projects and Innovation - EVERSIA	
EVERSIA	https://www.laverdad.es/	
SOLP	https://www.solplast.com	
CETEC	https://www.ctcalzado.org/en_US	https://twitter.com/CetecCentro
CETBIO	http://www.cetecbiotechnology.es/	
REGE	https://regeneralevante.com/proyectos/agro2circular-territorial-circular-systemic-solution-for-the-upcycling-of-residues-from-the-agrifood-sector/	https://twitter.com/REGENERA_ESE/status/1480893655632252935?s=20
TCA	http://www.tecnoalimenti.com/	
INFO	https://www.institutofomentomurcia.es/web/portal/agro2circular-kom	
EVRY	https://evrythng.com	https://twitter.com/EVRYTHNG

Partner Short Name	LinkedIn Channel involved in dissemination of projects' contents (link)	External discussion groups the partner participates to (LinkedIn groups, Facebook groups, forums, blogs...)
KVeloce	https://www.linkedin.com/company/k-veloce	https://www.youtube.com/user/kveloceidi
EURADA		
EVERSIA	Eversia: Publicaciones LinkedIn	
EVERSIA		
SOLP	https://www.linkedin.com/company/solplast-s-a/mycompany/	
CETEC	LinkedIn CETEC	
CETBIO		
REGE	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6886659691523436545	
TCA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/tecnoalimentis.cp.a./?originalSubdomain=it	YouTube (private channel)
INFO		
EVERY	https://www.linkedin.com/company/evrythng	Innovation Blog (https://evrythng.com/blog/) Videos (https://evrythng.com/videos/) Newsrooms (https://evrythng.com/newsroom)

Partner ShortName	Other	Partner's Communication Manager (name, surname, email address)
KVeloce		Aran Blanco ablanco@kveloce.com
EURADA		Jerome Friedrichs, jerome.friedrichs@eurada.org
EVERSIA		Álvaro Estrada: alvaro.estrada@eversia.es Irene Montoya: irene.montoya@eversia.es
EVERSIA	Eversia, la innovación como pilar estratégico La Verdad	
SOLP		
CETEC	Facebook CETEC	Fuensanta Monzó: fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
CETBIO		Verónica Cánovas: v.canovas@ctcalzado.org
REGE		Víctor Fabregat: vfabregat@regeneralevante.com
TCA		Marianna Faraldi: m.faraldi@tecnoalimenta.com
INFO		
EVRY		Axel Norbelly: axel.norbelly@evrythng.com

